

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE 2.2

Compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies v1

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List of acronyms

CC	Climate change
CCLM	COSMO model in CLimate Mode, where COSMO means COnsortium for Small-scale MOdelling
CDDA	Common Database on Designated Areas
EEA	European Environment Agency
EU	European Union
GALP	Fisheries Local Action Group (<i>Grupo de Acción Local de Pesca</i> , in Spanish)
GDP	Gross domestic product
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPCC SRES	IPCC Special Report on Emissions Scenarios
NA	Not available
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
RSC	Regional Sea Convention
SAC	Special Area of Conservation
SCI	Site of Community Importance

See acronyms of the participating partners in the table below.

Project information

Project full title: Moving ForwARd to achieving CLIMATE-resilient and sustainable European regional economic systems - FARCLIMATE

Acronym: FARCLIMATE

Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01

Topic: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01-04 - Transformation of regional economic systems for climate resilience and sustainability

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List of participants:

Partner No.	Organization Name Acronym
1 (Coord.)	UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO UVIGO
2	CONTACTICA S.L. CTA
3	INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURE IUCN
4	C4G - CONSULTING AND TRAINING NETWORK, LDA C4G
5	INVIALE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L. INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION GGG
8	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE ULIEGE
9	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON CESEFOR
10	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA UNL
11	FUNDACIÓN PARA LA PESCA Y MARISQUEO FUNDAMAR FUNDAMAR
12	European Network of Living Labs ENOLL
13	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS CERTH
14	Laurea University of Applied sciences LAUREA

Deliverable details

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Abstract:	The FARCLIMATE project tackles the multifaceted challenges of fostering climate resilience across Europe by implementing innovative solutions. Deliverable 2.2. provides the description and results of the first months of work of Task 2.2. Selection of case studies, and in it the criteria to be applied for the selection of the case studies, the results of the geospatial climate change risk analysis to define priority areas, the compilation of the potential case studies and a preliminary description of the first case studies selected for the project are presented.

Version	Date	Description
1	08/04/2024	This document describes the process followed in the first months to make the selection of case studies for the project, including the definition of criteria and the selection of the first group of cases. This is version 1.

Executive summary

This deliverable provides the description of 9 criteria to be applied for the selection of the case studies, the results of the geospatial climate change risk analysis to define priority areas, the compilation of 22 potential case studies and a preliminary description of the first 11 case studies selected for the project.

The defined criteria include: 1) Relevance of the case for Climate Change Adaptation, 2) Actual implementation, 3) Accessibility and relevance of information, 4) Thematic coverage, 5) Avoiding maladaptation, 6) Local and sub-national scales, 7) Multi-sectorial approaches, 8) Relationship with FARCLIMATE partners and willingness to participate, and 9) Quality of content.

Regarding the results of the climate risk mapping, in the fishery sector, regions with the highest climate change (CC) risk, particularly in Southern Europe, are identified due to the combination of variables related to climate impacts and adaptive capacity. Notable areas include Northern Spain, Southern Portugal, Southern France, Northern Italy, and others with a high percentage of protected areas. Similarly, the agricultural sector in Southern Europe faces significant CC risks, with countries like Spain, Portugal, Romania, and others highlighted due to their key agricultural importance and vulnerability. In the forestry sector, Southern Europe and Northern Europe stand out for CC risks, with countries like Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Poland, and Germany containing high-risk regions.

From the 22 potential case studies identified, 11 have been selected and preliminary described for this first stage. Six case studies are located in Spain, and one each in the following countries: Montenegro, Portugal, Albania, Poland, and Italy. Three will be focused on the agricultural sector, three on the forestry sector, three on the fishery sector, and two will be focused on both the forestry and agricultural sectors.

At least nine additional case studies will be defined for M18 in Deliverable D2.7 – Compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies v2. This deliverable will also review, complete, and improve, when necessary, the current selection of 11 case studies.

1. Introduction

D2.2 Compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies v1 is one of the main results of Task T.2.2 Selection of case studies. The document begins by providing a description of the nine criteria to be applied for the selection of the case studies (Chapter 3). The methodology, data, results, and conclusions from the geospatial climate change risk analysis are included in Chapter 4. The compilation of potential case studies, which was selected through the mobilization of the FARCLIMATE network of partners, is listed in Section 5. Finally, Chapter 6 includes a preliminary description of the 11 selected case studies.

2. Selection criteria for the case studies

Nine criteria have been defined for selecting and maintaining case studies for FARCLIMATE with the first five being considered as the main inclusion/exclusion criteria (eligibility criteria) and the other four considered as qualifying criteria. All criteria are meant to support the overall quality and consistency of case studies and develop an overall catalogue covering diverse climate change impacts, sectors, and European regions. The criteria have been developed based on Climate-ADAPT criteria ([criteria_09082023.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)).

(1) Relevance of the case for Climate Change Adaptation

According to the Climate-ADAPT criteria, the cases have been developed in response to climate change challenges. In this manner, maps were produced as a result of the data geoprocessing showing the European regions with a higher climate risk. This means, most vulnerable, most affected, and least adapted until now to climate change impacts, and therefore more of a priority for this analysis (Ara Begum et. al., 2022). Thus, these regions constitute a good reference point for selecting the case studies within them, even though this is not an exclusion criterion. Some case studies may be identified that are located outside those areas identified through the geoprocessing of data because they address or respond to specific climate change challenges, with an approach that brings novelty, innovation or relevance to other regions. In this case, detailed information will be provided to demonstrate and justify their suitability to take part in the project.

Spatial climate risk criteria for the geoprocessing at NUTS3¹ follow the AR6² risk-framework of the IPCC, incorporating the role of responses to climate change in modulating the determinants of risk (Figure 1).

¹ NUTS3 is the most detailed level of the NUTS classification (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics), a hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU (and the UK).

² Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) of the United Nations (UN) Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2023)

Figure 1. The IPCC Risk-Framework. Source: Simpson et al., 2022.

(2) Actual implementation

The selected cases have to present already ongoing adaptation measures/initiatives that could be of interest to the project or be willing to design and test new ones.

(3) Accessibility and relevance of information

FARCLIMATE case studies aim to share knowledge and practical experience for peer-to-peer learning across Europe. Information on the cases should therefore be easily accessible and (re-) assessment and evaluation should be feasible.

(4) Thematic coverage

The selection process should aim at including an equal number of case studies from these three different sectors: agriculture, fishery, and forestry. Activities related with extensive livestock farming could be also included.

(5) Avoiding maladaptation

Case studies must not refer to initiatives of maladaptation. In this sense, initiatives described in case studies to address vulnerability of one location must not increase the vulnerability of other locations. Moreover, adaptation measures should not further increase emissions of greenhouse gasses (strengthening the causes of climate change), damage the most vulnerable groups of population, create disproportions among different social groups, and conflict with environmental and sustainability policy goals.

(6) Local and sub-national scales

Sub-national and local are the scales of specific interest since sub-national and local authorities, and cities, are the main intended end users of the information to be obtained and capitalised from the case studies.

(7) Multi-sectorial approaches

Adaptation initiatives described in case studies will seek to focus on a specific economic sector or on several ones. Cases including a multi-sectorial, or an ecosystem-based approach should be considered with particular interest.

(8) Relationship with FARCLIMATE partners and willingness to participate

Having direct contact with one or more people working for the institution/organization who could potentially be involved and wish to participate in the project, and who acts as an intermediate with a community/region is considered an advantage.

Their willingness to apply the Living Lab methodology can also be taken into account in this criterion, as a point in favour of choosing the case study.

(9) Quality of content

Case studies with a complete description of all the aspects of the adaptation process are preferred. Description should include for example: information on sufficient stakeholders' participation, clear identification of the reference scenario(s) considered, clear consideration of the relevant legal and institutional frameworks, evidence of multi-benefits beyond adaptation, contribution to the sustainable development and transformative approach to adaptation.

3. Climate change risk mapping

Objective and methodology

The objective of this section is to perform a geospatial data analysis regarding the three economic sectors of interest - fishery, agriculture and forestry - in order to highlight the regions (NUTS3) with the higher climate change (CC) risk. As it was introduced in Section 2. for the eligibility of the study cases, the IPCC risk-framework was taken as a basis for this analysis. Therefore, data related to the four components of the risk - hazards, vulnerabilities, exposures and responses - was included in the analysis. These data were divided according to economic sector to obtain separate maps (Figure 2). Additionally, the database Key Biogeographic Regions was included in the analysis, as an auxiliary layer, to know the bioregion of the regions NUTS3 to ensure geographical balance in the selection of the study cases.

	FISHERY	AGRICULTURE	FORESTRY
Hazard	Potential environmental impact of CC	Potential environmental impact of CC Potential economic impact of CC on agriculture and forestry	Potential environmental impact of CC Potential economic impact of CC on agriculture and forestry
Exposure	Percentage of coast regarding the perimeter of the region	Percentage of agricultural lands	Percentage of forests
Vulnerability	Percentage of employment corresponding to the fishery sector (NUT2)	Percentage of GDP corresponding to the agricultural sector (NUT2)	Percentage of forests (using as equivalence of employment in forests)
	Percentage of the coast included as Marine Protected Area	Percentage of protected areas	Percentage of protected areas
Response	Adaptive capacity to CC	Adaptive capacity to CC	Adaptive capacity to CC
Auxiliary layer	Key Biogeographic Regions	Key Biogeographic Regions	Key Biogeographic Regions

Figure 2. Compilation of the databases used in the geospatial analysis of the climate change risk. In rows, databases are grouped by role of the IPCC risk-framework and the auxiliary layer. In columns, databases grouped by economic sectors of interest for the analysis. Note that the number of databases can be different depending on the sector and role, due to data availability. Source of databases: EEA geospatial data catalogue, ESPON toolbox, Eurostat.

Once selected the databases, the CC risk was obtained through the weighting of the different roles (Figure 3). The weighting values were derived from practical considerations and output analysis, ensuring that the selected values were both suitable and reflective of the most important factors.

Figure 3. Weighted values corresponding to each database, including the processes applied for each of them to obtain the final output independently for the given economic sector of interest.

Database presentation

* Note that regions with Not available (NA) values in any of the datasets, will present NA values in the main output. These NA values depend on the geographical extent of the dataset.

Fishery

A. Potential Environmental Impact of Climate Change

Definition: Potential impact of changes in summer and winter precipitation, annual mean temperature and annual mean evaporation on the environment.

Methodology: Impact calculated as a combination of regional exposure to climatic changes and recent data on regional sensitivity. Climatic changes derived from comparison of 1961-1990 and 2071-2100 climate projections from the CCLM (COSMO model in CLimate Mode, where COSMO means CONSORTIUM for Small-scale MODelling) model for the IPCC SRES (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change - Special Report on Emissions Scenarios) A1B scenario.

Release date: 2006

Source: [Indicator: Potential environmental impact of climate change | ESPON Database Portal](#)

This dataset was obtained from the mean of four subdatasets:

- Potential impact of climate change on soil organic carbon content: Potential impact of changes in summer and winter precipitation, annual mean temperature and annual mean evaporation on soil organic carbon content.

- Potential impact of changes in heavy rainfall on soil erosion: Potential impact of changes in heavy rainfall days on soil erosion sensitive areas.
- Potential impact of climate change on Natura 2000 protected areas: Potential impact of changes in summer and winter precipitation, heavy rainfall days, annual mean temperature, summer days, frost days, snow cover days and annual mean evaporation on Natura 2000 protected areas.
- Potential impact of climate change on forest fires: Potential impact of changes in summer days and summer precipitation on forests prone to fire.

Figure 4. Map of the potential environmental impact of climate change on the coastal regions at NUTS3 level.

Table 1. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of potential environmental impact of CC in the coastal region. Where the higher the value, the higher the impact.

POTENTIAL ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF CC			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
EL633	EL	Ileia	0.39
PT150	PT	Algarve	0.34
ES120	ES	Asturias	0.333
ES111	ES	A Coruña	0.326
PT111	PT	Alto Minho	0.317
...
SE110	SE	Stockholms län	0
SE214	SE	Gotlands län	-0.003
SE321	SE	Västernorrlands län	-0.012
FI196	FI	Satakunta	-0.017
FI195	FI	Pohjanmaa	-0.033

B. Percentage of coast regarding the perimeter of the region

Definition: Percentage of coastline in comparison with the total perimeter of the NUTS3 region, under the 2021 NUT version.

Methodology: Obtained only the coastal regions of the European Union (EU) at NUTS3 level, the lines corresponding to the coastline were split using GIS processes. Then, the distance of the coastline in meters for each region, was compared with the perimeter of the given region in meters. As a result, the percentage was obtained.

Release date: 2021

Source: Own elaboration using the data published in [NUTS - GISCO - Eurostat \(europa.eu\)](https://nuts.gisco.europa.eu)

Figure 5. Map of the percentage of coast regarding the perimeter of the region at NUTS3 level.

Table 2. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of the percentage of coast regarding the perimeter of the region at NUTS3 level. Where 1 means that the total perimeter is coast, such as islands; and close to 0 means that the coastline is minimum.

PERCENTAGE OF COAST REGARDING THE PERIMETER OF THE REGION			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
ES706	ES	La Gomera	1
CY000	CY	Kýpros	1
ES707	ES	La Palma	1
ES708	ES	Lanzarote	1
ES709	ES	Tenerife	1
...
BE211	BE	Arr. Antwerpen	0.026
EL521	EL	Imathia	0.025
PT185	PT	Lezíria do Tejo	0.02
UKJ46	UK	West Kent	0.01
BE236	BE	Arr. Sint-Niklaas	0.005

C. Percentage of employment corresponding to the fishery sector (NUTS2)

Definition: Employment in Fisheries, 2009

Methodology: Employment in fisheries is presented for all EU28+4 coastal regions as a percentage of total employment. The values are grouped into five classes, ranging from 0.22-0.52% up to 1.20-8.27%. The data for fisheries includes employees working in Fishing and aquaculture (marine and freshwater), Processing and preserving of fish etc., Production of oils and fat, Manufacture of prepared meals and dishes, Manufacture of cordage, rope, twine and netting, Manufacture of machinery for food, beverage and tobacco processing, Repair of other equipment, Wholesale of other food, included fish, crustaceans and molluscs, Retail sale of fish, crustaceans and molluscs in specialised stores, Technical testing and analyses, Research and experimental development on natural sciences and engineering.

Release date: 2009

Source: Own elaboration through visual interpretation from the figure published in [Employment in Fisheries, 2009 | Map Finder \(espon.eu\)](#). Values of this database were normalized in order to a better performance in the analysis.

Comments: Note that the values are the same for every NUTS3 region under the same NUTS2 region, since the maximum accuracy of this database was NUTS2.

Figure 6. Map of the percentage of employment normalized corresponding to the fishery sector (NUTS2).

Table 3. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of the percentage of employment normalized corresponding to the fishery sector (NUTS2). Where each value corresponds to the comparison of the percentage of each given region to the region with the maximum percentage.

PERCENTAGE OF EMPLOYMENT CORRESPONDING TO THE FISHERY SECTOR (NUT2) - normalized			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
IS002	IS	Landsbyggð	1
IS001	IS	Höfuðborgarsvæði	1
UKM50	UK	Aberdeen City and Aberdeenshire	0.47
ES111	ES	A Coruña	0.458
ES114	ES	Pontevedra	0.458
...
ITI17	IT	Pisa	0.043
FI1D7	FI	Lappi	0.043
UKD47	UK	Chorley and West Lancashire	0.043
ITI11	IT	Massa-Carrara	0.043
ITF51	IT	Potenza	0.043

D. Percentage of the coast included as Marine Protected Area

Definition: Percentage of the coastline of each NUTS3, which is included in a buffer of 1 km around the Marine Protected Areas.

Methodology: Having the coastline for each NUTS3 region version 2021, a buffer of 1 km was applied in the Marine Protected Areas. The coastline included in this buffer was considered as a coast under protection status. Finally, the percentage of protected coast in comparison with the coastline of each region was obtained. The Marine Protected Areas are those established under the framework of the EU Nature directives (Natura 2000), Nationally designated areas (Common Database on Designated Areas -CDDA-), and the Regional Sea Conventions (RSC) as reported in the respective official spatial and tabular databases.

Release date: 2022

Source: Own elaboration through the data published in [EEA geospatial data catalogue \(europa.eu\)](https://eod.europa.eu)

Figure 7. Map of the percentage of the coast included as Marine Protected Area for each NUTS3 region.

Table 4. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of the percentage of the coast included as Marine Protected Area for each NUTS3 region. Where 1 means that the total coast is protected, and 0 means that the total coast is under no protection.

PERCENTAGE OF THE COAST INCLUDED AS MARINE PROTECTED AREA			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
DE947	DE	Aurich	1
DE94A	DE	Friesland (DE)	1
DE94H	DE	Wittmund	1
PL426	PL	Koszaliński	1
DE94C	DE	Leer	1
...
NL323	NL	IJmond	0
NL324	NL	Agglomeratie Haarlem	0
EL302	EL	Dytikos Tomeas Athinon	0
IT135	IT	Fermo	0
IT133	IT	Macerata	0

E. Adaptive capacity to climate change

Definition: Combination of economic, infrastructural, technological, institutional capacity and knowledge and awareness of climate change.

Methodology: Weighted combination of economic capacity (weight 0.21), infrastructure capacity (0.16), technological capacity (0.23), knowledge and awareness (0.23) and institutional capacity (0.17). Weights are based on a Delphi survey of the ESPON Monitoring Committee.

Release date: 2005

Source: [Indicator: Adaptive capacity to climate change | ESPON Database Portal](#)

Figure 8. Map of the percentage of the adaptive capacity to climate change for each NUTS3 region.

Table 5. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of the adaptive capacity to climate change for each NUTS3 region. Where the higher the value, the higher the adaptive capacity.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY TO CC			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
DK011	DK	Byen København	1
DK012	DK	Københavns omegn	0.982
DK013	DK	Nordsjælland	0.971
SE110	SE	Stockholms län	0.959
DK014	DK	Bornholm	0.957
...
ITF63	IT	Catanzaro	0.423
ITF65	IT	Reggio di Calabria	0.42
ITF61	IT	Cosenza	0.42
ITF64	IT	Vibo Valentia	0.418
EL645	EL	Fokida	0.409

F. Key Biogeographic Regions

Definition: Biogeographical regions.

Methodology: The biogeographical regions dataset contains the official delineations used in the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and for the EMERALD Network set up under the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Bern Convention). Biogeographical boundaries were obtained from the EU Member States and from the Emerald Network countries. These were merged together to produce a European wide map of the biogeographical regions independent of political boundaries. A number of the regions were updated during the work under Article 17 of the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and in 2010 the Standing Committee to the Bern Convention adopted a number of changes according to progress in the setting-up of the Emerald Network.

Release date: 2023

Source: [Biogeographical regions \(europa.eu\)](http://biogeographicalregions.europa.eu)

Figure 9. Map of the Key Biogeographic regions in the coast at NUTS3 level.

Agriculture

A. Potential Environmental Impact of Climate Change

Definition: Potential impact of changes in summer and winter precipitation, annual mean temperature and annual mean evaporation on the environment.

Methodology: Impact calculated as a combination of regional exposure to climatic changes and recent data on regional sensitivity. Climatic changes derived from comparison of 1961-1990 and 2071-2100 climate projections from the CCLM model for the IPCC SRES A1B scenario.

Release date: 2006

Source: [Indicator: Potential environmental impact of climate change | ESPON Database Portal](#)

It was obtained from the mean of four subdatasets:

- Potential impact of climate change on soil organic carbon content: Potential impact of changes in summer and winter precipitation, annual mean temperature and annual mean evaporation on soil organic carbon content.
- Potential impact of changes in heavy rainfall on soil erosion: Potential impact of changes in heavy rainfall days on soil erosion-sensitive areas.
- Potential impact of climate change on Natura 2000 protected areas: Potential impact of changes in summer and winter precipitation, heavy rainfall days, annual mean temperature, summer days, frost days, snow cover days and annual mean evaporation on Natura 2000 protected areas.
- Potential impact of climate change on forest fires: Potential impact of changes in summer days and summer precipitation on forests prone to fire.

Figure 10. Map of the potential environmental impact of climate change at NUTS3 level regions.

Table 6. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of potential environmental impact of CC. Where the higher the value, the higher the impact.

POTENTIAL ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF CC			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
ES113	ES	Ourense	0.421
EL633	EL	Ileia	0.39
ES413	ES	León	0.376
PT150	PT	Algarve	0.34
ES120	ES	Asturias	0.333
...
FI194	FI	Etelä-Pohjanmaa	-0.001
SE214	SE	Gotlands län	-0.003
SE321	SE	Västernorrlands län	-0.012
FI196	FI	Satakunta	-0.017
FI195	FI	Pohjanmaa	-0.033

B. Potential Economic Impact of Climate Change on agriculture and forestry

Definition: Potential impact of climate change on agriculture and forestry.

Methodology: Impact calculated as combination of regional exposure to climatic changes and recent data on regional sensitivity. Climatic changes derived from comparison of 1961-1990 and 2071-2100 climate projections from CCLM model for the IPCC SRES A1B scenario.

Release date: 2006

Source: [Indicator: Potential impact of climate change on agriculture and forestry | ESPON Database Portal](#)

Figure 11. Map of the potential economic impact of climate change on agriculture and forestry at NUTS3 level regions.

Table 7. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of potential economic impact of climate change on agriculture and forestry at NUTS3 level regions. Where the higher the value, the higher the negative impact, being the values under zero considered as positive impact.

POTENTIAL ECONOMIC IMPACT OF CC ON AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
ITG18	IT	Ragusa	0.697
EL523	EL	Kilkis	0.645
EL524	EL	Pella	0.616
ITG17	IT	Catania	0.595
EL521	EL	Imathia	0.571
...
FI1D5	FI	Keski-Pohjanmaa	-0.747
FI196	FI	Satakunta	-0.785
FI1D7	FI	Lappi	-0.822
FI195	FI	Pohjanmaa	-0.905
FI200	FI	Åland	-1

C. Percentage of agricultural lands

Definition: Percentage share of agricultural areas in 2018

Methodology: Percentage share of agricultural areas per NUTS3 region in 2018 Corine classes: agriculture: all 200 (211, 212, 213, 221, 222, 223, 231, 241, 242, 243, 244)

Release date: 2018

 Source: [Indicator: Percentage share of agricultural areas in 2018 | ESPON Database Portal](#)

Figure 12. Map of the percentage of agricultural lands at NUTS3 regions.

Table 8. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of percentage of agricultural lands at NUTS3 level regions. Where the higher the value, the higher the percentage.

PERCENTAGE OF AGRICULTURAL LANDS			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
UKN07	UK	Armagh City, Banbridge and Craigavon	0.917
ITF44	IT	Brindisi	0.915
UKF30	UK	Lincolnshire	0.914
ITH56	IT	Ferrara	0.913
BE252	BE	Arr. Diksmuide	0.911
...
UKI31	UK	Camden and City of London	0
UKI32	UK	Westminster	0
UKI33	UK	Kensington & Chelsea and Hammersmith & Fulham	0
UKI34	UK	Wandsworth	0
FR105	FR	Hauts-de-Seine	0

D. Percentage of GDP corresponding to the agricultural sector (NUTS2)

Definition: Ratio between the agricultural production and the total Gross domestic product (GDP) of a given NUTS2 region.

Methodology: On the one hand, the GDP at current market prices by NUTS 2 regions is obtained; on the other hand, the output of the agricultural industry, which means the total number of hours worked in agriculture during the calendar year (in millions of €). This last dataset is obtained from the Economic accounts for agriculture by NUTS 2 regions. Once obtained the ratio, the values were normalized to a better performance in the analysis.

Release date: from 2010 to 2021 depending on data availability.

Source: Own elaboration through data obtained from [Statistics | Eurostat \(europa.eu\)](#) and [Statistics | Eurostat \(europa.eu\)](#)

Comments: Note that the values are the same for every NUTS3 region under the same NUTS2 region, since the maximum accuracy of this database was NUTS2.

Figure 13. Map of the percentage of GDP corresponding to the agricultural sector (NUTS2) normalized.

Table 9. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of percentage of GDP corresponding to the agricultural sector (NUTS2) normalized. Where each value corresponds to the comparison of the ratio of each given region to the region with the maximum ratio.

PERCENTAGE OF GDP CORRESPONDING TO THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR (NUT2) - normalized			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
BG315	BG	Lovech	1
BG311	BG	Vidin	1
BG312	BG	Montana	1
BG313	BG	Vratsa	1
BG314	BG	Pleven	1
...
DE300	DE	Berlin	0
PL911	PL	Miasto Warszawa	0
ES640	ES	Melilla	0
PL912	PL	Warszawski wschodni	0
PL913	PL	Warszawski zachodni	0

E. Percentage of protected areas

Definition: Share of protected areas in NUTS3 regions.

Methodology: Share of NUTS3 containing protected area according to WDPa protected area data.

Release date: 2019

Source: [Indicator: Share of protected areas in NUTS3 regions | ESPON Database Portal](#)

Figure 14. Map of the percentage of protected areas by NUTS3 regions.

Table 10. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of percentage of protected areas by NUTS3 regions.

PERCENTAGE OF PROTECTED AREAS			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
HR033	HR	Zadarska županija	1
SE110	SE	Stockholms län	1
HR032	HR	Ličko-senjska županija	0.95
DEB12	DE	Ahrweiler	0.948
BE345	BE	Arr. Virton	0.917
...
TRA24	TR	Ardahan	0
RS227	RS	Podunavska oblast	0
NL111	NL	Oost-Groningen	0
FR105	FR	Hauts-de-Seine	0
FR107	FR	Val-de-Marne	0

F. Adaptive capacity to climate change

Definition: Combination of economic, infrastructural, technological, institutional capacity and knowledge and awareness of climate change.

Methodology: Weighted combination of economic capacity (weight 0.21), infrastructure capacity (0.16), technological capacity (0.23), knowledge and awareness (0.23) and institutional capacity (0.17). Weights are based on a Delphi survey of the ESPON Monitoring Committee.

Release date: 2005

Source: [Indicator: Adaptive capacity to climate change | ESPON Database Portal](#)

Figure 15. Map of the percentage of the adaptive capacity to climate change for each NUTS3 region.

Table 11. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of the adaptive capacity to climate change for each NUTS3 region. Where the higher the value, the higher the adaptive capacity.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY TO CC			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
DK011	DK	Byen København	1
DK012	DK	Københavns omegn	0.982
DE21H	DE	München, Landkreis	0.971
DK013	DK	Nordsjælland	0.971
DE111	DE	Stuttgart, Stadtkreis	0.966
...
ITF64	IT	Vibo Valentia	0.418
RO314	RO	Giurgiu	0.415
EL645	EL	Fokida	0.409
RO317	RO	Teleorman	0.408
EL643	EL	Evrytania	0.395

G. Key Biogeographic Regions

Definition: Biogeographical regions.

Methodology: The biogeographical regions dataset contains the official delineations used in the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and for the EMERALD Network set up under the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Bern Convention). Biogeographical boundaries were obtained from the EU Member States and from the Emerald Network countries. These were merged to produce a European-wide map of the biogeographical regions independent of political boundaries. A number of the regions were updated during the work under Article 17 of the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and in 2010 the Standing Committee to the Bern Convention adopted a number of changes according to progress in the setting-up of the Emerald Network.

Release date: 2023

Source: [Biogeographical regions \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu)

Figure 16. Map of the Key Biogeographic regions in the coast at NUTS3 level.

Forestry

A. Potential Environmental Impact of Climate Change

The same as presented in section 4.2.2.A

B. Potential Economic Impact of Climate Change on agriculture and forestry

The same as presented in section 4.2.2.B

C. Percentage of forests

Definition: Share of Forests

Methodology: Share of Forests (Corine Land Cover nomenclature)

Release date: 2006

Source: [Indicator: Share of Forests | ESPON Database Portal](#)

Figure 17. Map of the percentage of forests at NUTS3 regions.

Table 12. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of percentage of forests at NUTS3 level regions. Where the higher the value, the higher the percentage.

PERCENTAGE OF FORESTS			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
SE221	SE	Blekinge län	0.741
AT223	AT	Östliche Obersteiermark	0.72
SE212	SE	Kronobergs län	0.7
BG424	BG	Smolyan	0.696
DEG04	DE	Suhl, Kreisfreie Stadt	0.686
...
DE94G	DE	Wesermarsch	0.002
BE256	BE	Arr. Roeselare	0.001
ES704	ES	Fuerteventura	0.001
TRC21	TR	Şanlıurfa	0.001
ES708	ES	Lanzarote	0

D. Percentage of forests (using it as equivalence of employment in forests)

Definition: Share of Forests

Methodology: Share of Forests (Corine Land Cover nomenclature). From this dataset, the values were normalized, to a better performance of the analysis.

Release date: 2006

Source: [Indicator: Share of Forests | ESPON Database Portal](#)

Comments: This dataset was used since it was not possible to find any data related with the economic relevance of forestry in each region, not at NUTS2 nor NUTS3. Then, this way was the only one that was found until now, considering that the more forest in a region should mean the more forest-related industry. Although it is known that this is not true for every region. Then, limitations of this information will be considered when analysing the results. In a second version of this geospatial analysis, a better dataset concerning the economic relevance of forestry in each region will be included if found.

Figure 18. Map of the percentage forests normalized.

Table 13. Maximum and minimum values of the dataset of percentage of forests. Where each value corresponds to the comparison of the ratio of each given region to the region with the maximum ratio.

PERCENTAGE OF FORESTS (used as equivalence of forestry employment) - normalized			
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value
SE221	SE	Blekinge län	1
AT223	AT	Östliche Obersteiermark	0.972
SE212	SE	Kronobergs län	0.944
BG424	BG	Smolyan	0.939
DEG04	DE	Suhl, Kreisfreie Stadt	0.925
...
DE94G	DE	Wesermarsch	0.002
BE256	BE	Arr. Roeselare	0.001
ES704	ES	Fuerteventura	0.002
TRC21	TR	Şanlıurfa	0.001
ES708	ES	Lanzarote	0.001

E. Percentage of protected areas

The same as presented in section 4.2.2.E

F. Adaptive capacity to climate change

The same as presented in section 4.2.2.F

G. Key Biogeographic Regions

The same as presented in section 4.2.2.G

Results and interpretation

Fishery

Figure 19. Map of CC risk categorized for the Fishery sector at NUTS3 level. Legend: High: values above 0.2; Medium: values between 0.1 and 0.2; Low: values between 0 and 0.1; Very low: values below 0.

Table 14. Maximum and minimum values of the CC risk categorized for the Fishery sector at NUTS3 level. Legend: High: values above 0.2; Medium: values between 0.1 and 0.2; Low: values between 0 and 0.1; Very low: values below 0.

CC RISK IN THE FISHERY SECTOR BY KEY BIOREGION					
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value	Category	BIOREGION
EL421	EL	Kalymnos, Karpathos, Kasos, Kos, Rodos	0.325	High	Mediterranean
ES111	ES	A Coruña	0.308	High	Atlantic
PT150	PT	Algarve	0.304	High	Mediterranean
EL621	EL	Zakynthos	0.295	High	Mediterranean
EL624	EL	Lefkada	0.294	High	Mediterranean
...
FRD21	FR	Eure	-0.04	Very low	Atlantic
FI1D5	FI	Keski-Pohjanmaa	-0.046	Very low	Boreal
DEF02	DE	Kiel, Kreisfreie Stadt	-0.054	Very low	Continental
DEF0E	DE	Steinburg	-0.055	Very low	Atlantic
DK012	DK	København omegn	-0.063	Very low	Continental

As it was mentioned in the methodology, different variables were taken into account when obtaining the CC risk in the fishery sector. In this sense, these variables are directly related with the obtained output. Looking at Figure 19, the majority of the regions with higher risk are in Southern Europe, including Atlantic, Mediterranean and Black Sea regions. Having in mind that these regions are the ones more affected by the climate change impact and with the lower climate change adaptive capacity, it makes sense. While the economic impact of fishery varies across these areas, it is particularly significant in Northern Spain and Central Greece. Nevertheless, it is because of the percentage of protected areas that the risk increases. Then, the coast corresponding to Northern Spain, Southern Portugal, Southern France, Northern Italy, Balearic Islands, Sardinia, Corsica, Bulgaria and Romania seem areas to put interest on them.

Focusing on the rest of Europe, one region situated in the Netherlands and two more in Germany call for attention. Same as before, the combination of the variables results in values to put interest on them. Also, with less importance, but still relevant for being Northern Europe, some regions in Estonia, Atlantic France and Ireland are highlighted.

Given this, with this geospatial analysis, the selection of the study cases can be performed. Not only choosing the regions with the higher CC risk in the fishery sector, but also, being able to select cases in different biogeographical regions, that can be pilot studies for other regions.

Agriculture

Figure 20. Map of CC risk categorized for the Agriculture sector at NUTS3 level. Legend: High: values above 0.2; Medium: values between 0.1 and 0.2; Low: values between 0 and 0.1; Very low: values below 0.

Table 15. Maximum and minimum values of the CC risk categorized for the Agriculture sector at NUTS3 level. Legend: High: values above 0.2; Medium: values between 0.1 and 0.2; Low: values between 0 and 0.1; Very low: values below 0.

CC RISK IN THE AGRICULTURE SECTOR BY KEY BIOREGION					
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value	Category	BIOREGION
BG325	BG	Silistra	0.361	High	Continental
BG325	BG	Silistra	0.361	High	Steppic
BG323	BG	Ruse	0.359	High	Continental
PT184	PT	Baixo Alentejo	0.354	High	Mediterranean
BG314	BG	Pleven	0.323	High	Continental
...
FI196	FI	Satakunta	-0.235	Very low	Boreal
FI1D9	FI	Pohjois-Pohjanmaa	-0.241	Very low	Boreal
FI1D5	FI	Keski-Pohjanmaa	-0.242	Very low	Boreal
FI195	FI	Pohjanmaa	-0.269	Very low	Boreal
FI200	FI	Å...land	-0.272	Very low	Boreal

Looking at Figure 20, the majority of the regions with higher risk in the agricultural sector are in Southern Europe, including in the Mediterranean, Continental, Black Sea and Steppe biogeographic regions. Same as in the previous sector, having in mind that Southern Europe is the most affected by the climate change impact and with the lowest climate change adaptive capacity, it makes sense. Even more when the dataset focused on the impact on forestry and agriculture completely highlights this area. Also, countries such as Spain, Portugal, Romania, Greece, Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary and Poland stand out as countries where the agricultural sector is key. As a result, these already mentioned countries, adding France and Italy, are the ones with the highest risk. These last two countries are important also because agriculture areas are large there. Not to mention the regions with a high percentage of protected areas that, of course, are taken into account too.

Focusing on the rest of Europe, included as regions with medium risk, several ones are distributed along Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, Austria and Slovakia. Same as before, the combination of the variables results in values to put interest on them. It is worth mentioning that the Atlantic biogeographic region is included here too.

Given this, with this geospatial analysis, the selection of the study cases can be performed. Not only choosing the regions with the higher CC risk in the agricultural sector, but also, being able to select cases in different biogeographical regions, that can be pilot studies for other regions.

Forestry

Figure 21. Map of CC risk categorized for the Forestry sector at NUTS3 level. Legend: High: values above 0.2; Medium: values between 0.1 and 0.2; Low: values between 0 and 0.1; Very low: values below 0.

Table 16. Maximum and minimum values of the CC risk categorized for the Forestry sector at NUTS3 level. Legend: High: values above 0.2; Medium: values between 0.1 and 0.2; Low: values between 0 and 0.1; Very low: values below 0.

CC RISK IN THE FORESTRY SECTOR BY KEY BIOREGION					
NUTS3	COUNTRY	REGION	Value	Category	BIOREGION
SI038	SI	Primorsko-notranjska	0.324	High	Alpine
SI038	SI	Primorsko-notranjska	0.324	High	Continental
SI038	SI	Primorsko-notranjska	0.324	High	Mediterranean
SI037	SI	Jugovzhodna Slovenija	0.301	High	Alpine
SI037	SI	Jugovzhodna Slovenija	0.301	High	Continental
...
DE273	DE	Kempton (Allgäu), Kreisfreie Stadt	-0.163	Very low	Continental
LV006	LV	Rīga	-0.164	Very low	Boreal
DK012	DK	Københavns omegn	-0.171	Very low	Continental
DK011	DK	Byen København	-0.179	Very low	Continental
DK014	DK	Bornholm	-0.199	Very low	Continental

Looking at Figure 21, same as in the previous sectors the majority of the regions with higher risk in the forestry sector are in Southern Europe, but not only.

Focusing firstly on this former region, it is known that Southern Europe is the most affected by the climate change impact and with the lowest climate change adaptive capacity, and also the highest impact on forestry and agriculture. Additionally, in these Southern countries, vast extensions of forests are presented, some of them largely protected. As a result, countries such as Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Slovenia, Greece, Bulgaria and Romania contain the majority of the regions with High and Medium CC risk.

But also, Northern Europe is important in terms of CC risk in forestry. Countries such as Poland, Germany and Belgium present areas with High risk, in addition to other countries such as Sweden, Slovakia, Hungary and Austria that also present Medium risk regions. Maybe the CC impact here is not as high as in the South of Europe, but given the large extension of forest, and the large number of protected areas, they are also included.

Given this, in the forestry sector geospatial analysis there are several study cases with enough conditions to be chosen that represent almost every biogeographic region under Medium or High CC risk. Atlantic, Mediterranean, Continental, Alpine, Boreal, Black Sea, Pannonian and Steppe are included. Just Macaronesia, Arctic and Anatolian are discarded. So, the selection of pilot studies in different biogeographical regions in this sector is ensured.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that in this analysis, the economic impact of the forestry sector was obtained directly from the percentage of forested areas in the region. Then, these results are not completely reliable.

OUTPUT RESOURCES EXPLANATION

As a result of the geospatial analysis, the following resources were generated:

- Maps. Every variable included in the analysis is included, in addition to the main output (Risk impact of CC of the given sector and Risk categories) and the auxiliary variable showing the KeyBioRegions. All are available in image format (.png).
- Csv and Shapefiles. They contain the numeric information of every variable included in the analysis. Here, the values can be checked more in detail, and a vectorial layer (.shp) is available.

4. Potential case studies

For the identification of the case studies, a preliminary list of potential cases was collected using the networks of the FARCLIMATE partners. For each preliminary case study, the sector, country, geographic location, and internal and external focal points were identified. In this regard, the internal focal points are entities that are project partners or associated partners of the FARCLIMATE projects, and the external focal points are local entities, not partners/associates of FARCLIMATE, that will facilitate the case study. It should be noted that not all the information was defined for all the case studies, as some will be selected for Deliverable D2.7 – Compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies v2 in M18. A total of 22 potential case studies were defined in this first step of the process as it is specified in Table 17.

Table 17. List of potential case studies.

No	Geographic location	Internal Focal Point	External Focal Point	Country	Sector
1	Turin Municipality	GGG	To be defined	Italy	Agriculture
2	Gorenjska Region	ENoLL	Local Energy Agency of Gorenjska (LEAG)	Slovenia	Agriculture
3	Tarczyn Municipality	UVIGO	Tarczyn City Council – Municipality of Tarczyn & Development Policy Foundation	Poland	Agriculture
4	Vlora Municipality	UVIGO	Vlora City Council	Albania	Agriculture and forestry
5	Fundao Municipality	FUNDAO	Fundao Municipality	Portugal	Agriculture and forestry
6	Ria de Arousa	UVIGO	GALP (Grupo de Acción Local de Pesca)	Spain	Fishery
7	Ria de Pontevedra	UVIGO	GALP (Grupo de Acción Local de Pesca)	Spain	Fishery
8	Roman metropolitan area	UVIGO	Roman Metropolitan area city council	Rumania	Agriculture and forestry
9	Riaza Region	Cesefor	To be defined	Spain	Forestry
10	Tejo Estuary	Fundamar	To be defined	Portugal	Fishery
11	Campania Region	GGG	To be defined	Italy	Agriculture
12	Emilia-Romagna Region	Fundamar	To be defined	Italy	Fishery
13	Inland Galicia	Cesefor	GDR (Grupo de Desarrollo Rural)	Spain	Forestry
14	Cataluña region (to be confirmed)	IUCN	Fundación Savia	Spain	Forestry
15	To be defined	IUCN	Fundación Aula del Mar Mediterráneo	Spain	Fishery
16	Dehesa San Francisco in Huelva Province	IUCN	Fundación Monte Mediterráneo	Spain	Forestry
17	Malaga Province	IUCN	Diputación de Málaga	Spain	Forestry
18	To be defined	IUCN	Diputacion de Sevilla	Spain	Agriculture
19	Kotor Bay	IUCN	Environmental Protection Agency of Montenegro	Montenegro	Forestry
20	Troyes Champagne Métropole	UVIGO	To be defined	France	Agriculture
21	ILVO (Marine Living Lab)	EnoLL	To be defined	Belgium	Fishery
22	To be defined	IUCN	Fundacion lonxanet	Spain	Fishery

From this list of potential case studies, a first selection has been made by applying the criteria so that in this first stage the cases for which there was sufficient information available to be able to assess whether it is a case of interest for the project and could qualify against the criteria have been pre-selected. So the first selection of cases includes cases with sufficient information, with relevant adaptation actions already underway or imminent, with interest and possibility to participate, with already initiated or solid contact with a project partner, covering the sectors of interest for the project, and, as far as possible, covering the widest possible variety of approaches, scales (national and sub-national) and different territories. The quality of the descriptive content of the case study has been attempted to be as good as possible, although at this stage of work on the case study list the information is not yet available in the detail needed for most of them.

In the project proposal the initial selection was for 9 case studies, but it has been considered that from the list of potential cases, 11 of them could already be selected in this first phase.

In section 5 the information for these 11 cases is provided. This information has been provided by the case study managers themselves or local entities - external focal points - preferably, and if not possible, by the FARCLIMATE partner familiar with and in contact with the case study (internal focal point). To collect the necessary background information, an online questionnaire or e-survey has been developed and sent out (<https://forms.gle/8iSu3RWBP19peqQq6>).

The case studies that the partners saw the most potential to be integrated in this first stage have been contacted by email briefly introducing the FARCLIMATE project (including the brochure presenting the project), explaining that the case could be relevant as an example of adaptation and inviting them to fill in the online form to give us more information if the collaboration would be of interest to them.

5. Description of the case studies

This section includes a brief description, in the form of a fact sheet, of each of the 11 case studies that have been pre-selected in this first phase.

Each factsheet contains brief information on the sector that would be targeted and its characteristics in the case study, on the climate change challenges it faces, and on measures implemented or planned to address them. The “Institution/organization” field refers to the one who filled out the form and provided the information.

The level of detail of the information provided depends on what each focal point in the case study has provided. At this stage there is some disparity in the level of detail of each case, but for the time being there is sufficient information for this first stage of selection. In the coming months (and for the second version of the deliverable) more detailed information will be available for those cases where it is scarcer.

CASE STUDY 1	
General information	
Institution/organization	Fundación Savia por el Compromiso y los Valores
Location	Cataluña region (to be confirmed), Spain
Sector	Agriculture and forestry
Specific information	
Main characteristics of the sector	
The increase in average temperatures, reduced water availability, abandonment of traditional agricultural, livestock and forestry techniques are leading to a loss of biodiversity and the abandonment of rural villages.	
Climate change challenges the sector currently faces	
Climate challenges that the agriculture and forestry sector are facing include loss of biodiversity/habitats, extreme temperatures, changes in land use, and water management issues. These challenges result in drought, depopulation, contamination of aquifers, loss of native breeds, and loss of ecosystems.	
Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.	
Enhancement of the Dehesa ecosystem, defence of extensive livestock farming, proposal for the creation of the “Defender of Future Generations” figure.	

CASE STUDY 2	
General information	
Institution/organization	Cesefor (External focal point to be defined)
Location	Riaza Region, Spain
Sector	Forestry
Specific information	
Main characteristics of the sector	
<p>The forestry sector is a strategic sector in the fight against climate change as it offers a renewable product (wood) as a substitute for polluting materials (coal, gas, oil, cement, steel, etc.). It is a sector with great growth potential as a small percentage of forest growth is cut. It also has growth potential in wood-based product innovation. Climate change may negatively affect the sector due to the specialisation of the industry and possible future changes in the suitability of forest species in the territory.</p>	
Climate change challenges the sector currently faces	
<p>The forest sector faces numerous climate-related challenges, including droughts, extreme temperatures. Additionally, it experiences loss of productivity, biodiversity, diseases, and pests, leading to a general decline of forest species and increased risk of forest fires.</p>	
Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.	
<p>Implementation of close-to-nature forestry techniques as a means of adapting stands to climate change and increasing the quality of forest products. Also, a commitment to the management of mixed as opposed to monospecific stands.</p>	

CASE STUDY 3	
General information	
Institution/organization	Diputación de Málaga
Location	Málaga Province, Spain
Sector	Agriculture and forestry
Specific information	
Main characteristics of the sector	
<p>Málaga Provincial Council (<i>Diputación</i>) works mainly with municipalities of less than 20.000 inhabitants of this province. Its role is to support them in the development of the services they must provide to citizens. The Climate Change Department works closely with these municipalities, which are highly affected by climate change. Malaga Provincial Council published in 2023 the Malaga Province Climate Change Adaptation Plan (AdaptaMálaga Plan; https://www.malagaviva.org/8445/adaptacion-al-cambio-climatico). Also, the Regional Government of Andalucía is working together with all the Andalusian Provincial Councils on Municipal Climate Change Plans (mitigation and adaptation) for those municipalities of less than 50.000 inhabitants.</p> <p>The main sectors in which we are involved are: rural environment; depopulation due to climate issues; bio economy, circular economy and biomass linked with forestry (forest environment); tourism and climate shelters.</p> <p>Diputación de Málaga has been working since 2016 on the Málaga Viva Strategy https://www.malagaviva.org to implement climate change adaptation measures.</p>	
Climate change challenges the sector currently faces	
<p>Various climate-related challenges, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loss of biodiversity due to lack of water, fires and extreme temperatures. • Consequences of droughts for biodiversity, agriculture and climate comfort of citizens • Health consequences in population due to extreme temperatures • Floods • Changes in tourism demand • Reduction of CO2 emissions and promotion of energy efficiency through circular economy in forest environments and through innovative sustainable mobility measures and plans. 	
Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.	

Relevant initiatives:

-Since 2016, Málaga Viva Strategy is developing its Climate Change adaptation measures. In its mission to fight climate change, it has established three strategic objectives:

- Improve the environment, guaranteeing the maintenance of the province's biodiversity as well as the reduction of atmospheric emissions.
- Contribute to rising awareness of existing environmental problems and, therefore, to the dissemination to all territories of best environmental practices that contribute to combating climate change.
- Build networks of associations, companies and individuals who share the common goal of combating climate change to unify resources, disseminate knowledge and promote the exchange of experiences and good practices.

-Málaga Viva Action Plan, with nine strategic axes:

- Territorial planning and coordination
- Energy efficiency
- Sustainable management of solid urban waste
- Sustainable management of water
- Renaturalisation and CO2 capture
- Sustainable mobility
- Training, community sensitization and awareness raising
- Social Innovation
- Best practices in Málaga Provincial Council internal functioning

-Malaga Province Climate Change Adaptation Plan (AdaptaMálaga Plan)

-Plan Bio+A Málaga: objective: to promote circular economy around bioeconomy sector in forest environments in Málaga Province, through sustainable forest management, promoting biodiversity, protection of ecosystems and the use of biomass in the province for heating. Diputación de Málaga is working in this strategy since 2020 and has recently received the approval to develop some of the activities with funds from Next Generation EU (from Fundación Biodiversidad). We are also working in installing biomass heaters.

- Studies for the creation of a provincial network of climate shelters for the population during extreme temperature episodes.

- Sustainable Mobility Plans for municipalities of less than 20.000 inhabitants.

CASE STUDY 4	
General information	
Institution/organization	Fundación Monte Mediterráneo
Location	Dehesa San Francisco in Huelva Province, Spain
Sector	Agriculture and livestock
Specific information	
Main characteristics of the sector	
<p>The dehesas of Spain (in Portugal called montados) are human-made ecosystems characterized by a savannah-like structure and very high biodiversity, where the trees (mainly holm oak, <i>Quercus ilex</i>) are viewed as an integrated part of the system, and as a result are planted, managed and regularly pruned. They are traditionally grazed by mixed livestock at low densities, and are probably one of the oldest agroforestry systems still in existence in Europe.</p> <p>The dehesa is the last barrier to the desert and a very delicate and multifaceted agro-sylvo-pastoral system, endangered by mismanagement, overgrazing, erosion, deforestation and disease and pest/infestation. The disappearance of the dehesa will increase climate change, and at the same time these ecosystems are highly impacted by climate change.</p>	
Climate change challenges the sector currently faces	
<p>Spain is facing significant challenges due to climate change, particularly in the South where the iconic dehesa ecosystem is found. Loss of biodiversity and habitats, exacerbated by droughts, erosion, and the disappearance of the dehesa, are pressing concerns. Extreme temperatures and fires further compound these issues. Changes in agricultural practices and water management, along with livestock management, are crucial in addressing these environmental challenges</p>	
Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.	
<p>Initiatives related to transhumance, reforestation, vulture conservation, the organic management of 700 hectares of dehesa, and the organic certification of mountain meadows in North Spain.</p>	

CASE STUDY 5	
General information	
Institution/organization	Municipality of Vlore
Location	Municipality of Vlore, Albania
Sector	Agriculture and forestry
Specific information	
Main characteristics of the sector	
<p>The predominant agricultural features of the municipality of Vlore include vineyards covering 30%, olive groves occupying 60%, and vegetables accounting for 10% of the territory. Significant challenges arise within the viticultural sector, primarily attributed to climate change. Numerous vineyards face abandonment and removal due to damages incurred and the diminished profitability of selling the produce.</p>	
Climate change challenges the sector currently faces	
<p>Changes in Agricultural Practices and Water Management</p> <p>Over the years, there has been a tendency to plant foreign cultivars that are not suited to the local soil and climate, especially in response to climate change. In addition, there have been cases of drought, vineyard damage and decreased production due to hailstorms that occurred at inopportune times.</p>	
Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.	
<p>No measures have been taken to support climate change adaptation. We are drafting and will formalize the Local Climate Change Adaptation Plan.</p>	

CASE STUDY 6	
General information	
Institution/organization	Environment Protection Agency of Montenegro
Location	Kotor Bay, Montenegro
Sector	Fishery
Specific information	
Main characteristics of the sector	
<p>As one of the main hotspots in the Adriatic region, Montenegro is experiencing an intensification of environmental changes, threatening marine resources critical to local communities. In response, adaptation strategies and research promoted by the Institute of Marine Biology in Kotor play a key role in helping these communities. This support is becoming increasingly vital as communities not only face climate-related pressures, but also competition from other sectors, notably the burgeoning tourism industry, including cruise ships. The balance between marine ecosystem conservation and economic sustainability emerges as a pressing concern, requiring collaborative efforts and innovative solutions to safeguard both livelihoods and environmental integrity.</p>	
Climate change challenges the sector currently faces	
<p>Fishers and producers of mussels and oysters in the Bay of Kotor, Montenegro, face significant challenges in maintaining their livelihoods due to the impacts of climate change. The loss of biodiversity and habitat, exacerbated by extreme temperatures, poses a significant threat to marine ecosystems. In addition, rising sea temperatures, marine deoxygenation and acidification, exacerbated by pollution, further threaten the delicate balance of the bay's environment. Despite the natural mitigation provided by the inflow of fresh-water from the mountains into Kotor Bay, these challenges persist, underlining the urgent need for adaptation strategies and collaborative efforts to mitigate the negative impacts on both marine resources and livelihoods.</p>	
Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.	
<p>The Kotor Institute of Marine Biology leads research efforts, while corporate associations engage in activities to assist producers and fishers in adapting their practices to the changing environment of Kotor Bay.</p>	

CASE STUDY 7

General information

Institution/organization	Municipality of Fundão
Location	Fundão, Portugal
Sector	Agriculture and forestry

Specific information

Main characteristics of the sector

The municipality of Fundão boasts a flourishing agribusiness sector, with 3,235 companies operating in various sectors. Agriculture, animal production, hunting, forestry and fishing stand out, accounting for 21% of the total number of companies. This sector has also emerged as the third largest employer, highlighting its central role in the local economy.

The region's diverse terrain supports the production of high-quality endogenous products, such as cherries, wine, cheese, olive oil, honey and mushrooms, which contribute to an annual turnover of around EUR 100 million. Noteworthy is the production of Fundão cherries, which accounts for about 60% of national production and generates EUR 20 million per year for the local and national economy.

In addition, the municipality focuses on food processing and marketing, promoting local specialities such as Beira Baixa cheese, sausages, fruit juices and jams. Initiatives such as Casa do Mel support the beekeeping heritage, while investments in almond and cannabis production signal the modernisation and innovation of agriculture.

Regarding forested areas, the Serra da Gardunha of Fundão is of considerable ecological importance, designated as a Site of Community Importance (SCI) within the Natura 2000 network and recognised as a Special Area of Conservation (SAC) under the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC). This designation derives from its rich biodiversity, hosting species and plant communities of exceptional conservation value.

Fundão's commitment to sustainability and circular economy principles is evident through public and private investments, partnerships with entities such as CTT for digital sales channels and initiatives to promote the local gastronomic heritage. Despite the challenges posed by climate change, the municipality positions itself as a Living Lab for sustainable development, promoting innovation, collaboration and inclusive policies for a resilient future.

Climate change challenges the sector currently faces

The municipality faces various climate impacts and vulnerabilities, including high temperatures that cause dehydration and metabolic disorders, while cold waves lead to an increase in cold-related illnesses. Excessive rainfall causes flooding, traffic disruptions and infrastructure damage, while forest fires damage plantations and infrastructure. Extreme weather events are intensifying, accompanied by changes such as reduced frost hours, higher minimum temperatures and fewer days of precipitation, leading to soil erosion and reduced water availability in inland areas.

These changes pose a significant threat to the primary and forestry sectors, affecting fruit and livestock production. Future projections indicate potential crop losses within two decades, prompting consideration of adaptation or crop diversification. Rising temperatures alter phenology, affecting the life cycles of plants and animals and potentially increasing pests and diseases. This could reduce crop and livestock yields and ecosystem services.

Climate change also affects water availability in inland waters, with unpredictable rainfall patterns and intense storms. Fluctuations in water temperature impact the health of aquatic ecosystems, affecting the viability of aquatic organisms. These interconnected challenges highlight the urgent need for adaptation strategies, including crop diversification, infrastructure resilience and ecosystem management, to mitigate climate risks and safeguard livelihoods and biodiversity.

Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.

The AgroTech Centre in Fundão serves as a dynamic hub for agricultural innovation, with the objective of transforming the territory into a living laboratory for the technological advancement of rural activities. Through a diversified service structure, it facilitates business incubation, acceleration programmes and the experimentation of IoT technologies.

The Seminary's Experimental Farm is a testing ground for start-ups and community projects, with a focus on cherries, olives and grapes, and also offers training programmes in agro-forestry. Collaborations with academic institutions such as the Biotech Plant Lab and the Biocant Park further enhance research into plant biotechnology and the promotion of economic activities.

The installation of LoRa technology enables the deployment of IoT solutions throughout Fundão, supporting the Fundão Intelligent City programme.

The Smart Farming initiative aims to anticipate and effectively control pests, while the Quinta Ciência Viva das Cerejas e das Ideias promotes sustainable tourism and collaboration between producers, researchers and entrepreneurs.

Through this network of partnerships and continuous innovation, the centre aims to transfer knowledge to the market and promote the circular economy, ensuring the sustainable development of Fundão's agri-food sector.

CASE STUDY 8	
General information	
Institution/organization	Orme orti metropolitani torinesi
Location	Torino, Italy
Sector	Agriculture
Specific information	
Main characteristics of the sector	
<p>ORME ETS - ORTI METROPOLITANI is an association that operates as a network of urban gardens, farms, third sector associations, cooperatives and citizens focusing on horticulture and urban agriculture in Turin and its metropolitan area. The urban gardens considered relevant to the project are located in districts 6 and 7, i.e. Aurora and Barriera di Milano, due to their history and structure. This is an industrial and marginalised area, heavily polluted and lacking green spaces. Orme's presence aims to revitalize these areas, providing not just agricultural opportunities but also fostering social inclusion, environmental education, and job placement and promoting more sustainable models of urban living. The association facilitates participatory processes to empower members and citizens, constructing resilient communities and solidarity networks for equitable food access. Due to the scale and nature of urban gardens, a short agricultural value chain is implemented, which is vulnerable to climate change. The area and the short supply chain are affected by climate change, especially during periods of continuous rainfall, in summer and winter, due to the absence of adequate covers and plant protection systems. During spring, the region experiences prolonged periods of rainfall, which can hinder the growth of new crops and planting due to inadequate drainage. In summer, high temperatures and limited rainfall lead to soil dryness, posing challenges for the irrigation system.</p>	
Climate change challenges the sector currently faces	
<p>Climate change presents several challenges that impact both ecosystems and communities. Biodiversity and habitat loss is a significant problem, as changing weather patterns disrupt ecosystems, leading to habitat loss and endangering species. Temperature extremes exacerbate these challenges, with scorching summers causing soil desiccation and winter frosts halting planting efforts. Vulnerable communities struggle to manage and cope with these changes, finding it difficult to adapt to alternating periods of drought and flooding due to inadequate drainage systems. As climate change intensifies, addressing these challenges becomes imperative to ensure the resilience and sustainability of natural environments and human communities.</p>	
Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.	
N/A	

CASE STUDY 9

General information

Institution/organization	University of Vigo (internal focal point) for GALP Arousa
Location	Ría de Arousa, Spain (several municipalities in an estuary)
Sector	Fishery

Specific information

Main characteristics of the sector

The fishery sector in Galician *rias* (estuaries) is renowned for its rich marine ecosystem, fostering a thriving fishing and aquaculture industry that positions Galicia as a leader in European fisheries. Beyond its economic significance, this industry profoundly influences the socio-economic structure of the region, shaping demographics, culture, and institutions. The Ría de Arousa stands out as the widest and shallowest of the Galician rias, boasting diverse intertidal ecosystems and wetlands that support various maritime activities. Its strong socioeconomic reliance on the sea is evident through its thriving fishing sector, characterized by inshore fishing, shell-fishing, and extensive mussel cultivation. Home to one of Spain's largest fishing fleets, mainly comprised of artisanal boats, the region's coastal towns like Ribeira and Cambados serve as key fishing ports. Despite its maritime focus, the Ría de Arousa also benefits significantly from tourism, capitalizing on its natural beauty and protected areas like the Illas Atlánticas National Park. With 465 businesses in the fishing sector and a substantial portion of the local labour force affiliated with fishing and aquaculture, around 22.12% of the total, the industry plays a pivotal role in the region's economy and social fabric.

Climate change challenges the sector currently faces

As outlined in the local development strategy of the Fisheries Local Action Group (GALP) Arousa and through consultations with the industry, there exists uncertainty regarding the impacts of climate change on the marine environment and its resources. Alterations in marine ecosystems may disrupt the availability of fish and other marine resources, potentially reducing fishing yields and economic returns. Furthermore, such changes can lead to shifts in the distribution of marine species, making it challenging for fishers to target traditionally caught species. Extreme weather events associated with climate change, such as heatwaves and increased rainfall, can negatively affect shellfish resources in the ría, resulting in decreased populations of commercially valuable species and subsequent economic ramifications for the local economy. Additionally, the occurrence of new or intensified marine events like algae blooms or invasive species can disrupt fishing operations and damage fishing infrastructure. Changes in salinity and temperature due to climate-induced variations in weather patterns can induce thermohaline stress in marine organisms, impacting their growth, reproduction, and behaviour, thereby contributing to a decline in shellfish stocks. Moreover, events in adjacent ecosystems, such as alterations in river systems or the effects of wildfires on the local marine environment, can also have significant repercussions. Through dialogue with stakeholders within the GALPs, a lack of understanding regarding the implications of climate change on the natural environment and marine resources has been identified.

Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.

There are currently no recognized initiatives addressing this issue apart from those incorporated within the production plans of fishers' guilds or investments in equipment for sustainable fishing practices or the restoration of marine ecosystems. Nevertheless, interspecific interactions, such as those observed in seagrass meadows covering shellfish nursery habitats, can aid in alleviating the impacts of environmental stress. These interactions contribute to climate mitigation and enhance the resilience of coastal systems, ultimately leading to improvements in fishing productivity.

CASE STUDY 10

General information

Institution/organization	University of Vigo (internal contact point) for GALP Pontevedra
Location	Ría de Pontevedra, Spain (several municipalities in an estuary)
Sector	Fishery

Specific information

Main characteristics of the sector

The Ría de Pontevedra stands out for its greater socio-economic diversity and urbanization compared to other areas. Nevertheless, the ría and its associated economic activities remain pivotal for regional cohesion. It boasts the highest concentration of ports along the Galician coast, with fishing and shellfish farming playing significant roles in towns like Campelo and Bueu. Tourism is also a major contributor, with Sanxenxo serving as a prominent tourist destination in northern Spain. Additionally, industrial activity is notable, with facilities such as a pulp mill and the Port of Marín handling containers. Geographically, the fishing area of these municipalities covers 292 km² and is inhabited by 77,279 people, representing nearly half of the total population. Protected areas within the ría and its islands include the National Park of Illas Atlánticas, Spanish Special Conservation Areas, and Special Areas for Bird Protection. The fishing sector comprises 268 businesses, employing 6.27% of the total workforce affiliated with social security in the fishing and aquaculture sector.

Climate change challenges the sector currently faces

According to the local development strategy in the GALP Pontevedra, fisheries resources and biodiversity are affected by climate change.

Alterations in marine ecosystems may disrupt the availability of fish and other marine resources, potentially reducing fishing yields and economic returns. Furthermore, such changes can lead to shifts in the distribution of marine species, making it challenging for fishermen to target traditionally caught species. Extreme weather events associated with climate change, such as heatwaves and increased rainfall, can negatively affect shellfish resources in the *ría* (estuary), resulting in decreased populations of commercially valuable species and subsequent economic ramifications for the local economy. Additionally, the occurrence of new or intensified marine events like algae blooms or invasive species can disrupt fishing operations and damage fishing infrastructure. Changes in salinity and temperature due to climate-induced variations in weather patterns can induce thermohaline stress in marine organisms, impacting their growth, reproduction, and behaviour, thereby contributing to a decline in shellfish stocks. Moreover, events in adjacent ecosystems, such as alterations in river systems or the effects of wildfires on the local marine environment, can also have significant repercussions. Through dialogue with stakeholders within the GALPs, a lack of understanding regarding the implications of climate change on the natural environment and marine resources has been identified.

Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.

No initiatives beyond those integrated into the production plans of fishers' guilds or the acquisition of machinery for sustainable fishing practices and marine ecosystem restoration are currently known. However, interspecific interactions, such as seagrass meadows covering shellfish nursery areas, can alleviate environmental stress. These interactions promote climate mitigation and coastal system resilience while enhancing fishing productivity. The functional coherence of GALP de Pontevedra is exemplified by a group of "cofradías" jointly managing fishing and shellfish resources in the Ría through coordinated exploitation plans outlined in the General Plan for Shellfish Exploitation 2021-2023. For instance, Bueu, Portonovo, and Aldán-Hío collaborate on shellfish exploitation, while Pontevedra, Lourizán, Raxó, and Marín have a joint plan for vessel management. Similarly, Pontevedra, Lourizán, and Raxó share a plan for regulating on-foot shellfish harvesting.

CASE STUDY 11

General information

Institution/organization	Municipality of Tarczyn & Development Policy Foundation
Location	Tarczyn Municipality, Poland
Sector	Agriculture

Specific information

Main characteristics of the sector

Sub-case study 1: the intensive apple farms in Tarczyn and the adjacent municipalities: the individual farm scope, certified BIO, and conventional farms.

Sub-case study 2: the "largest apple orchard in Europe": the area's scope/landscape conservation.

Climate change challenges the sector currently faces

Loss of biodiversity/habitats, Droughts, Extreme temperatures, Fires, Changes in agricultural uses, Water Management Challenges, Social innovation Culture and agricultural food traditions, landscape management & stewardship.

We are keen to host the living lab on-farm climate change adaptation, which is scoped on the apple orchard/s. Exploring:

1. How to mitigate/curb the loss of pollinators & ensure the pollination ratio under unpredictable spring weather: e.g. cover crops /early blossoming inter rows/reintroduction of bumblebees/ cooperation with apiculture;
2. To enhance soil-based water retention, limiting the impact of dry spells and prolonged droughts, the local cover crops mix;
3. To limit the impact of uneven, unpredictable patch precipitation: 70% under the hyper-intensive outpours: requiring costly re-spraying: propagation of integrated pest management practices/ e.g. pheromone traps + new training / trellising systems of the orchards and beyond.

Sub-case study 1: The climate-related challenges include: 1. Cumbersome and uneven pollination patterns due to the loss of pollinators and the late frosts; 2. Low soil-based water retention, dry spells and prolonged droughts; 3. Uneven, unpredictable patch precipitation: 70% under the hyper-intensive outpours/storms.

Sub-case study 2: The climate-related + intensive horticulture-related challenges include: 1. Low soil-based water retention, dry spells and prolonged droughts threaten the inter-field ponds' sustainability/drying out ; 3. Uneven, unpredictable patch precipitation: 70% under the hyper-intensive outpours/ storms, causing heavy erosion and massive surface runoffs/ containing the pesticides; 4. Loss of habitats of the birds/amphibians/ reptiles; 5. Fragmentation / Loss of ecological corridors due to extreme edge / balk plough + fencing + loss of idle land + inter-field bushes, etc.

Provide some information on the most relevant climate change adaptation initiatives/measures that are currently being implemented.

1. Piloting cover crops /early blossoming inter rows/reintroduction of bumblebees; 2. Testing the adjusted pheromone traps.

We are discussing the measures and looking for funding to address them. Considering the above enlisted, we would be happy to host the living lab in the area of cooperative-spirit landscape conservation/ stewardship + praxis of tailored climate change adaptation toolkits as per : 1. Low soil-based water retention, dry spells and prolonged droughts threaten the inter-field ponds' sustainability/drying out ; 2. Uneven, unpredictable patch precipitation: 70% under the hyper-intensive outpours/ storms, causing heavy erosion and massive surface runoffs/ containing the pesticides; 3. Loss of habitats of the birds/amphibians/ reptiles; 4. Fragmentation / Loss of ecological corridors due to extreme edge / balk plough + fencing + loss of idle land + inter-field bushes/ wind breakers etc.

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